

Scaffold Osteosynthesis Concept for Comminuted Distal Radius Fractures

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Introduction

The Scaffold Osteosynthesis Concept

Volar plate can be employed, with the distal row of locking screws positioned at the subchondral bony level. Rather than aiming the screws to capture a specific bone fragment, the construct functions as a scaffold “net,” holding the entire comminuted fracture in a reduced and stabilized position.

Materials and Methods

Among 125 comminuted distal radius fractures (DRF) in the ICUC database as of January 2025, we identified 14 cases with a dorsal ulnar articular bone fragment and a fragmented radial styloid fragment. According to “the specific fragment fixation” concept, it should not be easy to achieve solid fixation of these 14 fractures using volar plating alone.

The scaffold concept was employed. Despite the poor screw-bone holding capability in the fragmented styloid fragment in all 14 cases, as well as the inadequate screw-bone holding power in the dorsal ulnar corner fragment in 6 out of the 14 cases, we were unable to detect reduction loss in any case (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Discussion / Conclusion

1. The Scaffold Concept emphasizes the preservation of the soft tissue, particularly on the dorsal surface.
2. Creation of the scaffold effect using the volar plate and the distal row of locked screws (Fig. 1) placed just under the distal radius joint cortex, the construct stabilizes the entire multifragmented fracture without the need to “capture” specific fragments.
3. The scaffold fixation allows for a more effective load distribution across the fracture.

Scaffold fixation aims to insert a VA locked plate (as a scaffold, subchondral screws) over the reduced fracture, making use of the radiolucent bone clamp for fracture retention (Fig. 2), without looking for perfect bone purchase into each one of the main fragments; considering that soft tissues are important to achieve fracture reduction, and to increase construct strength.

The radiolucent bone reduction forceps is placed over the dorsal surface, this not only aids in overall fracture reduction but also provides solid fracture retention while the scaffold is fully completed. This approach also allows for the preservation of the dorsal soft tissues attached to the small dorsal bony and articular fragments.

Figures

Fig. 1: VA locking screws inserted as a scaffold, close to the distal radius articular surface, but not pretending an optimal screw purchase into the different bone fragments.

Fig. 2: Radiolucent bone reduction forceps

	CASE ID	DUC Purchase	Radial styloid Purchase
1	VC-192	Poor	Poor
2	VC-640	Good	Poor
3	VC-108	Good	Poor
4	DC-544	Poor	Poor
5	DC-100	Good	Poor
6	DC-373	Poor	Poor
7	DC-972	Good	Poor
8	DC-245	Good	Poor
9	DI-465	Poor	Poor
10	DC-408	Good	Poor
11	DC-032	Good	Poor
12	DC-068	Good	Poor
13	DC-055	Poor	Poor
14	VC-045	Poor	Poor

8 Good

6 Poor

14 Poor

Fig. 3: Despite the 43% poor bone purchase at the dorso-ulnar bone fragment and the poor bone purchase in the radial styloid fragment, we did not detect any loss of reduction in any case.

Fig. 4: Case examples of good (ICUC® ID: 23-VC-640) and poor bone purchase of the dorsal-ulnar corner fragment (ICUC® ID: 23-DC-544).

References

1. A. Fernández Dell'Oca, & Jesse B. Jupiter. (2022). Scaffold Osteosynthesis: *Volar Plating of Distal Radius Fractures*. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/7051004>
2. *Revisiting the ICUC concept including a powerful Search Tool by Jesse Jupiter*. (n.d.). VuMedi. <https://www.vumedi.com/channel/icuc/tab/videos-129/video/revisiting-the-icuc-concept-including-a-powerful-search-tool-by-jesse-jupiter/>
3. Regazzoni, P., Jupiter, J., & Fernández, A. (2024). *The need to adapt publication formats: Concepts of the ICUC Study group*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056675>
4. Medoff RJ. *Essential radiographic evaluation for distal radius fractures*. Hand Clin. 2005 Aug;21(3):279-88. doi: 10.1016/j.hcl.2005.02.008. PMID: 16039439.
5. Themes, U. (2016, July 22). *Fragment-Specific fixation of distal radius fractures*. *Musculoskeletal Key*. <https://musculoskeletalkey.com/fragment-specific-fixation-of-distal-radius-fractures-2/>